

Synthesis of Furano Compounds : Part XXXII. Synthesis of Some β -Brazanquinones Derived from Natural Sources

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A synthesis of 2-methyl-10-methoxy- β -brazanquinone isolated by Schmid *et al.*, as one of the end transformation product of Chartreusin, is described. A new synthesis of β -brazanquinone is reported from 2-(*o*-methoxy)-benzylideneindan-1-one by ring expansion of the five membered ring through the related epoxide. Yet another synthesis of β -brazanquinone involving Friedel-Crafts reaction embraces the synthesis of 3, 4, 8, 9-tetramethoxy- and 3, 8, 9-trimethoxy- β -brazanquinone, previously derived from natural sources.

The experiments described in this communication originated from our desire to synthesise 2-methyl-10-methoxy- β -brazanquinone (I), which was isolated by Schmid *et al.*¹ as one of the end transformation product of Chartreusin (XI). No synthetic work has yet been reported to confirm the structure of the natural product or any of its derivatives.

- (I) $R_1 = \text{Me}, R_7 = \text{OMe}, R_2 = R_3 = R_4 = R_5 = R_6 = \text{H}$. (II) $R_1 = \text{Me}, R_7 = \text{OH}, R_2 = R_3 = R_4 = R_5 = R_6 = \text{H}$.
 (III) $R_1 = \text{Me}, R_5 = \text{OMe}, R_2 = R_3 = R_4 = R_6 = R_7 = \text{H}$. (IV) $R_1 = \text{Me}, R_4 = \text{Br}, R_7 = \text{OMe}, R_2 = R_3 = R_5 = R_6 = \text{H}$.
 (V) $R_1 = \text{Me}, R_4 = \text{Br}, R_7 = \text{OH}, R_2 = R_3 = R_5 = R_6 = \text{H}$. (VI) $R_2 = R_5 = R_6 = \text{OMe}, R_1 = R_3 = R_4 = R_7 = \text{H}$.
 (VII) $R_2 = R_3 = R_5 = R_6 = \text{OMe}, R_1 = R_4 = R_7 = \text{H}$. (VIII) $R_1 = R_6 = R_3 = R_4 = R_5 = R_6 = R_7 = \text{H}$.
 (X) $R_5 = \text{Ph}, R_1 = R_2 = R_3 = R_4 = R_6 = R_7 = \text{H}$. (IX) $R_5 = \text{Ph}, R_1 = R_2 = R_3 = R_4 = R_6 = R_7 = \text{H}$.

Condensation of 5-methylcoumarandione with *m*-methoxyphenacyl bromide in alcoholic sodium ethoxide followed by hydrolysis afforded the keto-acid (XII), which was cyclised *via* the acid chloride with anhydrous aluminium chloride in carbon disulphide solution to give the 2-methyl-8-methoxy- β -brazanquinone (III), isomeric with (I), the cyclisation having taken place *para* to the methoxyl group. None of the desired quinone (I) could be detected from the residues left on the purification of (III). An alternative experiment on the condensation of 2-methoxycarbonyl-3-methoxyphenacyl chloride (XV) with homosalicyl-aldehyde (XVI) in alcoholic sodium methoxide so as to obtain (XIII) also ended in failure. Attempted

1. E. Simontsch, W. Eisenhuth, O. A. Stamm and H. Schmid, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1960, **43**, 58.

condensation in acetone in presence of potassium carbonate led to the exclusive formation of the unsaturated ketone (XVII).

(XII) $R_1 = \text{COOH}, R_2 = \text{Me}, R_4 = \text{OMe}, R_3 = R_5 = \text{H}.$

(XIII) $R_2 = \text{COOMe}, R_3 = \text{Me}, R_4 = \text{OMe}, R_1 = R_5 = \text{H}.$

(XIV) $R_1 = \text{COOH}, R_2 = \text{Me}, R_3 = \text{Br}, R_4 = \text{OMe}, R_5 = \text{H}.$

(XVII)

(XVI)

Exploratory experiments on alternative routes were next undertaken. Thus 2-*o*-methoxybenzylideneindan-1-one (XVIII) prepared by the action of *o*-methoxybenzaldehyde on indanone-1 in presence of aqueous sodium hydroxide was smoothly converted into the oxide by alkaline hydrogen peroxide. This underwent ring expansion in the presence of boron trifluoride to the naphthalene derivative (XX) under carefully controlled conditions^{2,3}. This on treatment with pyridine hydrochloride afforded the hydroxybrazan, which afforded β -brazanquinone (VIII) on oxidation with chromic acid. This new synthesis could not, however, be applied with any success for the synthesis of Schmid's quinone (I) as, although the epoxide (XXIII) could be converted into the naphthoresorcinol (XXI), the subsequent treatment with pyridine hydrochloride led unaccountably to the formation of alkali insoluble products.

(XVIII) $R_1 = R_2 = \text{H}.$

(XIX) $R_1 = \text{OMe}, R_2 = \text{Me}.$

(XX) $R_1 = R_2 = \text{H}.$

(XXI) $R_1 = \text{OMe}, R_2 = \text{Me}.$

(XXII)

(XXIII)

Success was eventually achieved when 2-bromo-5-methoxyphenacyl bromide was condensed with 5-methylcoumarandione as before to give the keto-acid (XIV), which on cyclisation *via* the acid chloride gave a mixture of quinones (IV) and (V), which were separated.

2. J. W. Ager and R. Robinson, *Tetrahedron*, 1966, No. 7, 277.

3. H. O. House and R. L. Wasson, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, **78**, 4394.

Both on debromination with the aid of palladised charcoal and hydrogen followed by aerial oxidation afforded respectively (I) and (II). The former was identical with an authentic specimen very kindly provided by Prof. H. Schmid and the latter has also been reported by Schmid *et al.*

A new synthesis of β -brazanquinone was further developed by Friedel-Crafts condensation of the acid chlorides derived from coumarone-2, 3-dicarboxylic acids and benzene derivatives. Thus the acid chlorides (XXIV and XXV) gave

(XXIV) $R = Cl$, $R_1 = H$, $R_2 = OMe$. (XXV) $R = Cl$, $R_1 = R_2 = OMe$.

(XXVI) $R = OH$, $R_1 = H$, $R_2 = OMe$. (XXVII) $R = OH$, $R_1 = R_2 = OMe$.

(XXVIII) $R = OH$, $R_1 = R_2 = H$.

(XXIX)

(XXX)

on condensation with veratrole, the quinones (VI and VII), which were identical with the authentic specimens derived respectively from brazilin and haematoxylin. The new synthesis of dicarboxylic acids (XXVI and XXVII) are described in the experimental. The condensation of (XXVIII) with dibenzothiophene can theoretically lead to the quinones (XXIX and XXX), of these (XXIX) is actually formed. The structure of the products rests on desulphurisation with Raney nickel to 8-phenyl- β -brazanquinone (IX) which was proved different from synthetic 9-phenyl- β -brazanquinone (X), which would have been formed if the quinone in question had the alternative structure (XXX).

EXPERIMENTAL

All m.ps. and b.ps. are uncorrected. IR, UV and NMR spectra have been determined respectively on Perkin-Elmer Infracord, Model 237 (in KBr), Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer Model 137 (in 95% ethanol) and Varian A-60 (with TMS as internal standard).

5-Methyl-2-(3'-methoxybenzoyl)-coumarone-3-carboxylic acid (XII): To a cold solution of sodium (0.23 g.) in abs. ethanol (15 ml.) was added 5-methyl-coumarandione⁴ (1.5 g.) and after 30 mins. *m*-methoxyphenacyl bromide (2.29 g). The mixture was refluxed for 4 hr., cooled and hydrolysed with 10% aqueous sodium hydroxide (50 ml.). In course of heating a dark oil separated. The alcohol was removed and the mixture was diluted with water and filtered. The filtrate on acidification with hydrochloric acid gave the acid (XII). Crystallisation from ethanol afforded yellowish needles (2.6 g.), m.p. 157-8°. (Found: C, 69.80; H, 4.70. $C_{18}H_{14}O_5$ requires: C, 69.67; H, 4.55%).

4. K. Fries and G. Finck, *Ber. Deust. Chem. Ges.*, 1908, **41**, 4280.

2-Methyl-8-methoxy- β -brazanquinone (III): Anhydrous aluminium chloride (3 moles) was added to a cooled solution of the crude acid chloride, obtained from the *keto-acid* (XII; 1.0 g.), in dry carbon disulphide and the mixture kept in the cold for 24 hr., the carbon disulphide decanted off, and decomposed with iced hydrochloric acid. The brownish sticky solid separated was chromatographed over alumina (benzene solvent) and crystallised from benzene to afford the *quinone* (III) in yellowish needles, m.p. 252.5-53°. The second crop from the mother liquor on purification melted at 252°, mixed m.p. with the first crop was undepressed. The mixed m.p. of this quinone with Schmid's 2-methyl-10-methoxy- β -brazanquinone, m.p. 252° (very kindly provided by Prof. Schmid), was 225°, showing thereby that the two compounds were different. The I.R. spectra were also different. (Found: C, 73.82; H, 4.25; C₁₈H₁₂O₄ requires: C, 73.96; H, 4.14%). IR spectrum: 6.17 and 6.23 μ (1, 4-quinone).

Reductive acetylation: The above brazanquinone (0.05 g.) was heated under reflux with zinc dust (0.05 g.), fused sodium acetate (0.2 g.) and acetic anhydride (5 ml.) and poured into water. The residue repeatedly extracted with acetic acid and added to the water 2-Methyl-8-methoxy- β -brazan-6, 11-diacetate crystallised from acetic acid in white plates, m.p. 255-6°. (Found: C, 69.83; H, 4.65. C₂₂H₁₈O₆ requires: C, 69.83; H, 4.80%).

2-Methoxycarbonyl-3-methoxyphenacyl chloride (XV): 2-Carhomethoxy-3-methoxybenzoic acid⁵ (0.4 g.) was suspended in dry benzene (4 ml.) and a drop of pyridine was added, followed by oxalyl chloride (0.4 ml.). This mixture was left at room temp. for 4 hr., till complete dissolution took place. The excess solvent and the oxalyl chloride were removed under suction and the residue washed twice with dry benzene. The acid chloride melted at 106-8° (sealed tube). A suspension of the acid chloride in dry ether (5 ml.) was added with vigorous shaking to cooled ethereal solution of diazomethane (from 10 g. of nitrosomethylurea) and left overnight in a refrigerator. The excess diazomethane and the ether were removed under reduced pressure and the yellow diazoketone (m.p. 113-5° decomp.) was decomposed with ethereal hydrochloric acid. When the evolution of nitrogen stopped (4 hr.), the excess ether and hydrochloric acid were removed to give a reddish brown mass, which was left overnight after mixing with a little methanol. The separated white solid (m.p. 142-3°) on recrystallisation from methanol gave the desired *chloroketone* as white needles, m.p. 148-9°. (Found: C, 54.44; H, 4.55. C₁₁H₁₁O₄Cl requires: C, 54.44; H, 4.54%). IR spectrum: 5.73 μ (ester carbonyl) and 6.23 μ (keto carbonyl).

*2-(*o*-Methoxy)-benzylideneindanone- (XVIII)*: A mixture of α -indanone (0.25 g.), *o*-methoxybenzaldehyde (0.26 g.) and potassium hydroxide (30 ml.; 5%) was refluxed for 10 min., when yellow needles of the benzylidene derivative separated on the cooler part of the flask. It was then cooled, the yellow solid collected, washed with a few ml. of methanol and water. The crude product (0.43 g.) crystallised from ethanol in yellow shining needles, m.p. 130-31°. (Found: C, 81.64; H, 5.85. C₁₇H₁₄O₂ requires: C, 81.58; H, 5.64%). IR spectrum: 5.9 μ (α , β -unsaturated ketone). UV: λ max. 212.5, 310 and 355 m μ (log ϵ 4.38, 4.20 and 4.24 respectively).

Epoxide : To a solution of the foregoing benzylidene derivative (0.35 g.) in methanol (35 ml.) at 45-50° was added hydrogen peroxide (30%, 0.5 ml.) followed by cautious addition of aqueous potassium hydroxide (10%, 0.5 ml.). The mixture was then stirred for 5 hrs. at this temp. and then allowed to stand overnight in the refrigerator. The separated white shining crystals of epoxide were collected and washed with water. The mother liquor on dilution with large volume of water precipitated further quantity of the epoxide (total yield, 0.24 g). It crystallised from ethanol in white needles, m.p. 144-5°. (Found : C, 76.50; H, 5.80. $C_{17}H_{14}O_3$ requires : C, 76.67; H, 5.30%). IR spectrum : 8.08 μ (epoxide), 5.81 μ (indan-1-one). UV : λ max. 213, 254, and 290 m μ (log ϵ 4.43, 4.28 and 3.95 respectively). NMR spectrum in $CDCl_3$: aromatic protons (8 : 2-3.2 τ), methoxyl protons (3; 6.35 τ), proton of the oxirane ring (1; 5.28 τ) and singlets (2; at 6.94 and 7.05 τ), for methylene protons.

Rearrangement : To a vigorously stirred suspension of the epoxide (0.53 g.) in cyclohexane (20 ml.) was added boron trifluoride etherate (1.25 ml.) and the stirring continued for 30 min. The separated organic layer and the ethereal solution of the pasty residue were combined and washed with water and aqueous sodium hydroxide (3 \times 10 ml.). Acidification of the alkali layer gave a yellow solid which was dissolved in benzene and chromatographed over silica. On removal of benzene, a yellow oil was obtained which afforded shining yellow needles of 2-(*o*-methoxyphenyl)-1, 3-dihydroxynaphthalene (0.4 g.). It crystallised out from benzene in two different forms, yellow needles, m.p. 154-5°, and cubes. The naphthol gave a blood red ferric reaction. (Found : C, 76.52; H, 5.10. $C_{17}H_{14}O_3$ requires : C, 76.67; H, 5.30%). *Benzoyl derivative*, m.p. 153-6°, could not be obtained in analytically pure form. IR spectrum : 5.80 μ (aromatic ester carbonyl).

Cyclisation and oxidation (VIII) : The dihydroxy compound (0.2 g.) was heated with pyridine hydrochloride (2 g.) at 200-10° for 2½ hrs. The melt was cooled, acidified with dil. hydrochloric acid and heated on steam bath for 30 min. The crude product (0.15 g.) was dissolved in acetic acid (1 ml) and added to an aqueous solution of chromic acid (0.22 g). The mixture was heated for 2 min., and when the exothermic reaction had ceased, water was added to precipitate the yellow brazanquinone (0.1 g.). The m.p. and mixed m.p. of a crystallised sample from acetic acid was 239-41° (lit.⁶, 245°). (Found : C, 77.32; H, 3.32. Calc. for $C_{16}H_8O_3$: C, 77.41; H, 3.25%). IR spectrum : 5.99 and 6.03 μ . The spectrum showed the new synthetic product to be identical with the authentic one.

2-(2'-Methoxy-5'-methyl)-7-methoxybenzylideneindanone-1 (XIX) : 7-Methoxyindanone was condensed with 4-methoxy-*m*-tolualdehyde in an identical manner as with (XVIII). The crude *benzylidene derivative* was crystallised from acetic acid in yellow needles, m.p. 197.5-99.5°. (Found : C, 77.30; H, 6.12. $C_{19}H_{18}O_3$ requires : C, 77.53; H, 6.16%). IR spectrum : 5.92 μ (α, β -unsaturated ketone). This was converted into the *epoxide* (XXIII) as before, which crystallised from ethyl acetate in white needles, m.p. 173-75°. (Found : C, 73.64; H, 6.10. $C_{19}H_{18}O_4$ requires : C, 73.53; H, 5.85%). IR spectrum : 5.83 μ and 8.15 μ .

Rearrangement : The epoxide was submitted to rearrangement as before. The *naphthoresorcinol* (XXI) was crystallised from benzene, m.p. 203-5°. (Found : C, 73.36; H, 6.01; $C_{19}H_{18}O_4$ requires : C, 73.53; H, 5.85%).

6. J. N. Chatterjee, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1964, **31**, 101.

Attempted cyclisation : The above phenol was heated with ten times its weight of pyridine hydrochloride as before. The product thus obtained was insoluble in alkali (m.p. above 300°).

3-Methoxy-6-bromoacetophenone : This compound was prepared from 3-methoxy-6-bromobenzoic acid⁷ (16 g.) according to the process of Walker and Hauser⁸. The ketone distilled at 123°/0.5 mm., yield, 12 g. The 2, 4-dinitrophenylhydrazone crystallised in orange needles, m.p. 163.5° from ethyl acetate. (Found : C, 43.78; H, 3.30. C₁₅H₁₃O₅N₄Br requires : C, 44.01; H, 3.18%).

3-Methoxy-6-bromo- ω -bromoacetophenone : A solution of the above ketone (16.58 g.) in dry chloroform (50 ml.) was gradually treated (at 10-15°) with a solution of bromine (8.34 g.) in dry chloroform (25 ml.) and left for sometime in ice and then washed with 10% sodium carbonate soln. and then with water. The chloroform layer was dried and distilled to give the phenacyl bromide, b.p. 120°/0.4 mm. The bromoketone formed salt readily with pyridine.

Condensation of 3-methoxy-6-bromophenacyl bromide with 5-methylcoumarandione : Condensation of the above phenacyl bromide with 5-methylcoumarandione was effected as under (III). The keto-acid crystallised in yellow needles from acetic acid, m.p. 172.5-4.5°. (Found : C, 55.81; H, 3.48. C₁₈H₁₃O₅Br requires : C, 55.54; H, 3.34%). The 2, 4-dinitrophenylhydrazone crystallised in orange needles, m.p. 270-2°, from ethyl acetate. (Found : N, 9.56. C₂₄H₁₇O₈N₄Br requires : N, 9.84%)

Cyclisation : The keto-acid was cyclised to the quinone (IV) as before. TLC of this quinone over silica (benzene) showed the presence of two components, R_f = 0.68 and R_f = 0.55. These were separated by column chromatography over alumina first with benzene as eluent. The first fraction, lemon yellow in colour, melted at 269-70° and crystallised from acetic acid in rosettes of lemon yellow needles (0.095 g.) and was identified as 2-methyl-7-bromo-10-methoxy- β -brazanquinone (IV). (Found : C, 58.15; H, 3.0. C₁₈H₁₁O₄Br requires : C, 58.22; H, 2.97%). IR spectrum : 5.95 and 6.03 μ . The column was next eluted with ethanol to furnish a product which on crystallisation from acetic acid gave shining prismatic needles (0.055 g., m.p. 242-3°) of 2-methyl-7-bromo-10-hydroxy- β -brazanquinone (V).

Debromination : Catalytic hydrogenation of the impure quinone (IV: 0.05 g.) in acetic acid (15 ml.) was accomplished over 5% palladised charcoal (0.03 g.) when the quinone absorbed 10 ml. hydrogen at R.T.P. during 8 hr. The product was filtered, but the quinol was rapidly oxidised by air to the quinone. It was then freed from solvent and taken up in chloroform, washed with bicarbonate and water. The chloroform was removed to get a lemon yellow product (0.035 g.). TLC revealed the presence of two components, R_f = 0.43 and R_f = 0.15. These were separated by column chromatography as before. The first elute gave lemon yellow 2-methyl-10-methoxy- β -brazanquinone (I) which crystallised from acetic acid in clumps of needles, m.p. 248-9° (lit.¹, 252°). yield, 0.035 g. Mixed m.p. with a sample derived from natural product was 248.5-9.5°. (Found : C, 73.71; H, 4.21. Calc. for C₁₈H₁₂O₄ : C, 73.96; H, 4.14%). IR spectrum : 6.0 μ . The spectra of the synthetic compound and the

7. G. B. Bachmann and G. M. Picha, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, **68**, 1599.

8. H. G. Walker and C. R. Hauser, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, **68**, 1386.

product derived from natural source were identical. The column was then eluted with ethanol to get 2-methyl-10-hydroxy- β -brazanquinone (II) as golden yellow solid (0.006 g.). Crystallisation from acetic acid gave golden yellow elongated plates, m.p. 251-2° (reported 255°). IR spectrum : 5.98 and 6.09 μ .

Reductive acetylation : This was carried out as before. 2-Methyl-10-methoxy- β -brazan-6, 11-diacetate crystallised from acetic acid in white needles, m.p. 231-2°. (Found : C, 69.61; H, 4.91. $C_{22}H_{18}O_6$ requires : C, 69.83; H, 4.80%).

3, 8, 9-Trimethoxy- β -brazanquinone (VI) : To a solution (ice cooled) of 6-methoxycoumarone-2, 3-dicarboxylic acid chloride (obtained from 0.5 g. of 6-methoxycoumarone-2, 3-dicarboxylic acid) in carbon disulphide (10 ml.) was added freshly distilled veratrole (0.29 g) and finely powdered aluminium chloride (0.71 g.), and the mixture was heated on steam bath for 6 hr. The red aluminium complex separated was left overnight at room temp. On working up as usual, a brown sticky mass separated, which was washed with a little ethanol, dried and sublimed at 162°/4 mm. The orange yellow sublimate (0.05 g) crystallised from a large volume of ethanol in long slender golden yellow needles, m.p. 260-2° (lit.⁹, 260°). It was found identical with an authentic sample (mixed m.p. and superimposable i.r. spectra) (Found : C, 67.31; H, 4.3. Calc. for $C_{19}H_{14}O_6$: C, 67.45; H, 4.17%). IR spectrum : 6.02 μ .

Ethyl α -hydroxy- α' -(3-methoxy) phenoxy-maleate : To Sodium ethoxide, prepared from sodium (0.46 g.) and abs. ethanol (1 ml.) in abs. ether (5 ml.), was added freshly distilled ethyl oxalate (5.3 g. in 10 ml. abs. ether) with cooling. After 30 min., ethyl 3-methoxyphenylacetate (4.5 g. in 10 ml. abs. ether) was added and the mixture refluxed for 24 hr. The reaction product was then poured on ice and the ether layer, containing unchanged esters, was separated. The aqueous layer was extracted with ether (2 \times 10 ml.) and acidified to obtain a brown oil. The oil was extracted with ether (3 \times 20 ml.), washed with water, dried and the ether distilled off to get ca. 5.6 g. of the crude oxalo-ester which was used for the next operation.

6-Methoxycoumarone-2, 3-dicarboxylic acid (XXVI) : To the preceding crude ester (5.6 g.) a mixture of acetic acid (11.5 ml.) and conc. sulphuric acid (11.5 ml.) was added and left at room temp. for 12 hr. The dark brown product was warmed on steam bath for 15 min. and then poured on ice. The separated dirty yellow gummy mass on trituration with a little ethanol gave a crystalline solid (1.5 g.), m.p. 154-6°, found to be the acid-ester. (Found : C, 54.56; H, 5.13. $C_{11}H_{12}O_6$ requires : C, 55.0; H, 5.04%). IR spectrum : 5.75 and 6.07 μ .

Hydrolysis : The acid ester (1.5 g.) was hydrolysed by heating it for 30 min. with 10% aqueous sodium hydroxide solution. The solution was acidified with cooling to obtain the acid as a cream coloured solid. It crystallised from benzene-ethanol in white rectangular plates, (1.2 g.), m.p. 217-8° decomp. (lit.¹⁰, 219° decomp.). (Found : C, 55.76; H, 3.22. Calc. for $C_{11}H_8O_6$: C, 55.94; H, 3.41%). *Toluidide* : The dicarboxylic acid (0.2 g.) was treated with thionyl chloride (1 ml) in dry chloroform (5 ml.). After one hour excess thionyl chloride

9. St. v. Kostanecki and L. Lloyd, *Ber Deust. Chem. Ges.*, 1903, **36**, 2200.

10. G. W. Holton, G. Parker and A. Robertson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 2049.

and chloroform were removed and *p*-toluidine (1 g.) in dry acetone (5 ml.) was added to it. Copious evolution of hydrogen chloride took place and the yellow toluidide (0.21 g.) separated soon. It crystallised from methanol in pale yellow needles, m.p. 194-6°. (Found : N, 6.92. $C_{25}H_{22}O_4N_2$ requires N, 6.76%). Partial decarboxylation : The dicarboxylic acid (0.1 g.) was sublimed at 200°/12 mm., when 6-methoxycoumarone-3-carboxylic acid (0.02 g.) was obtained. The compound crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 175-7°. (Found : C, 62.49; H, 4.37. $C_{10}H_8O_4$ requires : C, 62.50; H, 4.20%).

3, 4, 8, 9-Tetramethoxy- β -brazanquinone (VII) : This quinone was obtained from the acid (XXVII) by the method employed for the synthesis of (VI). The quinone was, however, obtained in a poor yield, m.p. 259-61° (lit.⁹, 262°). (Found : C, 64.95; H, 4.32. Calc. for $C_{20}H_{16}O_7$: C, 65.21; H, 4.38%). IR spectrum : 6.02 μ (1, 4-quinone). It was found identical with an authentic sample (mixed m.p. and superimposable i.r. spectra).

6, 7-Dimethoxycoumarone-2, 3-dicarboxylic acid (XXVIII) : This acid was prepared as before from 2, 3-dimethoxyphenol¹¹, m.p. 245-6° decomp. (lit.¹⁰, 252° decomp.). (Found : C, 53.88; H, 3.61. Calc. for $C_{12}H_{10}O_7$: C, 54.14; H, 3.79%). Anilide : The anilide was obtained as before. It crystallised from acetic acid in yellow needles, m.p. 190-1°. (Found : N, 6.58. $C_{24}H_{20}O_5N_2$ requires : N, 6.73%). Partial decarboxylation : The dicarboxylic acid was decarboxylated as before and the product, 6, 7-dimethoxycoumarone-3-carboxylic acid, crystallised from aqueous ethanol, m.p. 169-70°. (Found : C, 58.98 ; H, 5.09. $C_{11}H_{10}O_5$ requires C, 59.46; H, 4.54%).

Condensation of coumarone-2, 3-dicarboxylic acid (XXVIII) with dibenzothiophene : The dicarboxylic acid (XXVIII)¹² was condensed with dibenzothiophene as before. The crude benzofurano (2, 3-b)-benzothiopheno (6, 7-b')-naphthoquinone-1, 4 (XXIX) was extracted with petroleum ether (3 \times 5 ml.) and the residue left was chromatographed over alumina (benzene) and finally crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. above 300°. (Found : C 74.33; H, 2.67. $C_{22}H_{10}O_3S$ requires : C, 74.58; H, 2.85%). It develops a Prussian blue colour in conc. sulphuric acid. Orientation of this quinone was established by desulphurisation reaction as mentioned below.

Desulphurisation : The foregoing quinone (1 g.) was suspended in ethanol (50 ml.) and to this Raney nickel (10 g) was added. This suspension was next refluxed on steam bath for 8 hr., and the product was filtered hot. Residue left behind was extracted with chloroform (2 \times 10 ml.) and was mixed with the main solution. On removal of the solvent, 8-phenyl- β -brazanquinone (IX; 0.07 g.) was obtained as yellow solid (crude), m.p. 247-50°. It imparted violet colour to conc. sulphuric acid. IR spectrum : 6.0 μ , 6.27 μ and 6.84 μ (phenyl nucleus).

Reductive acetylation : This quinone was reductively acetylated as before. The white diacetate crystallised from acetic acid in cluster of tiny needles, m.p. 235-7°. (Found : C, 75.96; H, 4.51. $C_{26}H_{18}O_5$ requires : C, 76.09; H, 4.42%).

11. F. Weygand, H. Waber and E. Maekawa, *Chem. Ber.*, 1957, **90**, 1879.

12. C. F. Koelsch and A. G. Whitney, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, **63**, 1762.

9-Phenyl- β -brazanquinone (X): The keto-acid required for the synthesis was obtained by condensation of coumarandione with *p*-phenylphenacyl bromide as described earlier. The yellow *2-(p-phenyl)-benzoylcoumarone-3-carboxylic acid* crystallised from glacial acetic acid in shining plates, m.p. 190-2°. (Found: C, 76.98; H, 4.19. $C_{22}H_{14}O_4$ requires: C, 77.18; H, 4.12%). The *2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone* crystallised from ethyl acetate in red prisms, m.p. 247-8°. (Found: N, 10.82. $C_{28}H_{17}O_7N_4$ requires: N, 10.68%).

Cyclisation: The foregoing keto-acid was cyclised as under (VII) to (X). It crystallised from acetic acid in yellow needles, m.p. 218-20°. Mixed m.p. with its 8-phenyl isomer was depressed by 20°. (Found: C, 81.50; H, 3.91. $C_{22}H_{12}O_3$ requires: C, 81.47; H, 3.73%).

6-11-Diacetoxy-9-phenyl- β -brazan: The quinone (X) was reductively acetylated as in the case of (III). The white *diacetate* was crystallised from acetic acid in clumps of white needles, m.p. 238-40°. Mixed m.p. with its 8-phenyl isomer was depressed by 15°. (Found: C, 75.95; H, 4.65. $C_{26}H_{18}O_5$ requires: C, 76.09; H, 4.42%).

One of the authors (O.P.J) is thankful to the University Grants Commission, New Delhi for providing with a fellowship. Authors are also thankful to Dr. S. K. Roy for the synthesis of (III).

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Received February 10, 1969
Revised MSS received December 15, 1969.